

METHODS FOR REDUCING THE TOXICITY OF SMOKING-OUT TOBACCO PRODUCTS

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Annotation: When smoking, a large number of chemical compounds are formed on the burning end of a cigarette, which smokers inhale with cigarette smoke, these compounds also enter the environment. Tobacco smoke is an aerosol consisting of micro particles composed of liquid droplets dispersed in the gas-vapor phase. It contains a large number of chemical compounds, about 4,000 of which have been identified and quantified.

Keywords: carbon monoxide, hydrocarbons, smoking affects

A burning cigarette is a unique chemical factory that produces several thousand different chemical compounds, including more than 40 substances that directly cause cancer, and more than a dozen substances that contribute to their occurrence. The gas components of tobacco smoke include carbon monoxide and dioxide, hydrogen cyanide, ammonia, isoprene, acetaldehyde, acrolein, toluene, nitrobenzene, acetone, hydrazine, hydrogen sulfide, prussic acid, aniline, pyridine,

carcinogenic carbohydrates and other substances. The phase of tobacco smoke containing solid particles mainly consists of nicotine, water and tar - tobacco tar. The composition of tobacco smoke resin includes 38 polycyclic hydrocarbons that cause cancer, among which nitrosoamines, aromatic amines, isoprenoids, pyrenes, benzpyrenes, chrysenes, anthracenes, etc. should be noted.

According to the working group of the International Agency for Research on Oncological Diseases, it has been established that the smoking process is carcinogenic to humans. About 85-95% of lung cancer cases in men are associated with smoking. In Europe, the proportion of deaths from lung cancer caused by tobacco smoking in men is 93%. In recent years, mortality from lung cancer in women has increased, due to the spread of smoking among the female population of the planet.

Widespread smoking among the female population in the United States has led to the fact that now women in this country are more likely to die from lung cancer than from breast cancer. The mortality rate from this disease is about 70 thousand people annually. In England over the past 25 years, the number of women with lung cancer has increased by 74%, in Germany over the past 10 years, the number of women with lung cancer has increased by 2 times. The mortality rate of smoking Russian women from this disease is 49%.

The use of tobacco products is one of the causes of the development of malignant diseases of the urinary system. Smoking increases the risk of developing cancer of the larynx, bronchi, lip, oral cavity and pharynx, esophagus, stomach, pancreas and other organs.

Studies conducted worldwide have revealed the following consequences of

smoking during pregnancy: an increase in the frequency of spontaneous miscarriages and premature births; an increase in the frequency of prematurity and low body weight in newborns; an increase in perinatal mortality of newborns; an increase in the number of congenital developmental defects; deterioration of the physical and mental development of the child.

It should be noted that fathers' smoking plays a certain role in the birth of children with malformations, since intensive smoking affects the quality of sperm. As a result of nicotine intoxication, most of the spermatozoa become not only sedentary, but also deformed, and their total number decreases, as a result of which a healthy beginning of the pregnancy process cannot be laid.

as a result of the study, a high involvement of female workers in tobacco smoking was established (60%). In the age group of workers aged 40 to 50, the prevalence of tobacco use was 77.8%. In the examined sample, a decrease in the age of the first tobacco sample was found, which corresponds to all-Russian trends. The study of respondents' awareness of the negative consequences of smoking showed that non-smoking respondents are more aware of the dangers of smoking compared to female smokers. The features of the prevalence of false beliefs in women, depending on smoking behavior and age, have been studied. Among women who smoke, large gaps in knowledge were found in women of the age group of 30-40 years.

As a result of the assessment of the intensity and stereotype of smoking, it was found that only one in five respondents formed an episodic form of smoking behavior. The smoking behavior of the remaining respondents is characterized by an average or large use of cigarettes. Strong nicotine dependence was detected in

33.3% of women smokers in the age group under 30 years, in 14.3% of women in the age group 40-50 years and in every tenth woman aged 30-40 years. The predominant motive of tobacco smoking among respondents is the desire to receive support in a difficult psych emotional situation, which may be due to both the nature of work and a reduced level of behavioral regulation. The study showed that non-smoking subjects more actively support anti-smoking measures.

Currently, the association of exposure to tobacco smoke components with the development of reproductive function disorders, including decreased fertility, early menopause, menstrual cycle disorders, and the risk of cervical cancer (especially in combination with early initiation of smoking) has been proven.

Smoking in a pregnant woman increases perinatal mortality and causes disorders of neonatal adaptation. Nicotine, having neurotoxicity, causes a delay in the development of the central nervous system and intrauterine fetal development; increases the risk of sudden death of infants and the risk of neuropsychiatric and functional disorders in children of smokers.

However, despite medical concerns, the prevalence of smoking remains high. Thus, according to statistics provided by WHO, in 2013 the number of smokers in the world was 1.1 billion people, including 950 million men and 177 million women. Thus, smokers accounted for 21% of the adult population of the countries of the world.

The implementation of such measures as the fight against illegal trade in tobacco products and the ban on the sale of tobacco products to minors and minors is largely determined, on the one hand, by the integrity and decency of trade

workers. On the other hand, the smoking behavior of trade workers, in which the proportion of women and young people is high, can be considered as advertising tobacco products, especially for children and adolescents. In addition, for trade enterprises, the smoking of employees causes lost profits and deterioration of the image of the enterprise, in particular, due to unauthorized breaks in work for "smoke breaks", the absence of workers in the workplace. The prevalence of smoking among trade workers has not been studied enough.

A comparison of the prevalence of myths about smoking among smokers and non-smoking women showed that some myths are common only among smokers, including the misconception that smoking helps to fight excess weight. It is among women who smoke that the most common myth is that smoking helps to cope with stress. 70.8% of women smokers agreed with this statement. And the myth that quitting smoking is easy, on the contrary, is more common among non-smoking subjects.

The analysis of the prevalence of myths about tobacco smoking by age groups confirmed the least awareness of the negative consequences of tobacco smoking among respondents in the age group of 30-40 years. So, in this age group, every tenth respondent reduces the danger of passive smoking, and 37% of respondents are convinced that it is easy to quit smoking. The myth that smoking relieves tension is common among 74% of respondents in the group of 30-40 years. It is noteworthy that in the group of smoking 40-50-year-old respondents there are no analyzed myths, except for the idea that smoking relieves tension.

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